

Morphometrical Study of Adult Human Cricoid Cartilage: A Cadaveric Study

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Abstract:

Introduction: The cricoid cartilage forms the base of the larynx and is the only cartilage in the larynx that completely encircles the airway. The dimensions of the cricoid cartilage can vary significantly. Therefore standard-sized endotracheal tubes used for intubation can damage the mucous lining of the laryngeal cartilages, making the diameters of the cricoid cartilage clinically important. As a result, understanding these diameters has become increasingly relevant in medical practice.

Materials and methods: The study examined the cricoid cartilages of formalin embalmed 20 cadavers (10 male and 10 female) aged between 50-70 years. All muscles, ligaments, and mucous membranes were removed prior to the analysis. The following measurements were taken: anteroposterior diameter (both outer and inner), transverse diameter (both outer and inner), height of the lamina and arch, and the thickness of the arch and lamina. These measurements were obtained using a Vernier calliper.

Results: Measurements of the cricoid cartilage showed significant differences between males and females. Males exhibited notably larger dimensions compared to females. In this study, both the inner and outer anteroposterior (AP) diameters were greater than the transverse diameter (TD), and these measurements were larger in males than in females.

Conclusion: The current study revealed that the AP diameter was greater than the TD diameter, with both measurements being slightly greater than those observed in other Indian populations. This morphometric data will be valuable in choosing the right endotracheal tubes for intubation and for surgical procedures involving the larynx.

Key Words: Cricoid Cartilage, Diameter, Endotracheal tube, Larynx, Morphometry

I. INTRODUCTION

Larynx is an organ of phonation and is made up of cartilages and membranes. The cartilages of the larynx are the unpaired cricoid, thyroid and epiglottic cartilages, and the paired arytenoid, cuneiform and corniculate cartilages. Thyroid, cricoid and most of the part of arytenoid cartilages are made up of hyaline cartilage and others are elastic fibrocartilage. Calcification of thyroid cartilage starts first after the 25th year, then of cricoid and arytenoid. The size of the larynx remains same in children. After the puberty, size increases in males compared to the females [1].

A comprehensive understanding of laryngeal anatomy is crucial for professionals engaged in the surgical treatment of the larynx. Knowledge of the measurements of the cartilages of larynx and trachea is essential for procedures such as transplantation, stenting, intubation, cricothyroidotomy, and endoscopic interventions [2]. This information may also aid in selecting the appropriate surgical tools and helps to prevent unnecessary injuries to the larynx. Subglottic stenosis and post-intubation stenosis of the lower respiratory tract were significant factors that prompted anatomists to focus on measuring the various cartilages, specifically the cricoid cartilage [3,4].

Cricoid cartilage forms the base of the larynx. It is the only cartilage of the larynx that forms a complete ring around the airway and is thicker and stronger than the thyroid cartilage. It has narrow anterior arch and broad posterior lamina. The dimensions of the cricoid cartilage exhibit considerable variability [5]. Previous studies showed a significant increase in the sagittal diameter after 15 years of age, compared to the coronal diameter which was more earlier [6]. Furthermore, a study also revealed that in certain female patients, the inner diameter of the cricoid ring may not accommodate the passage of a standard-sized tracheal tube without risking mucosal injury. Consequently, these patients may experience pressure necrosis on the medial aspect of the arytenoid cartilages as a result of tracheal intubation with standard-sized tubes [4]. Because of this, the diameters of the cricoid have gained importance clinically. There is currently limited literature on the measurements of the larynx and cricoid cartilage. Expanding the available information on cricoid cartilage measurements from different regions can enhance our understanding of changes in the dimensions of laryngeal cartilages. Additionally, having accurate measurements can assist in selecting the appropriate endotracheal tubes during procedures, thereby preventing unnecessary damage to the laryngeal cartilages.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study involved the cricoid cartilages from formalin embalmed 20 cadavers (10 male and 10 female) aged between 50-70 years. Study was conducted in the Department of Anatomy J.N. Medical College, Belagavi, Karnataka. Twenty larynges were extracted from the cadavers, after which the cricoid cartilages were separated. Careful dissection was performed to remove all muscles, ligaments and mucous membranes. The measurements were taken using Vernier caliper with an accuracy of 0.1 mm.

The following measurements were recorded⁷:

1. Inner anteroposterior diameter at the inner aspects of anterior and posterior walls of cricoid (**Figure 1**)
2. Outer anteroposterior diameter at the outer aspects of anterior and posterior walls of cricoid.
3. Inner transverse diameter measured as the maximum transverse diameter between inner walls. (**Figure 1**).
4. Outer transverse diameter measured as the maximum transverse diameter between outer walls.
5. The height of the cricoid arch was measured as the distance between the midpoints of its upper and lower borders. (**Figure 2**)
6. The height of the lamina determined by measuring the distance between the midpoint of the upper and lower borders of the cricoid. (**Figure 3**)
7. The thickness of the arch was determined by measuring the distance between its inner and outer surfaces.
8. The thickness of the lamina was measured by the distance between its inner and outer surfaces.

Statistical analyses 2.1- The data collected were analyzed using SPSS software version 23. First, we calculated the mean and standard deviation (SD) for the continuous variable. Next, we applied the Student's t-test to assess the differences between the groups, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$.

III. RESULTS

Measurements of the cricoid cartilage showed significant differences between males and females, with males having notably larger dimensions than females (**Table 1**).

3.1 Diameters of Cricoid- The inner anteroposterior (AP) diameter of the male cricoid was 19.85 ± 1.61 mm, while the female measurement was 14.84 ± 1.54 mm. The outer AP diameter for males was $28.99 \pm$

1.45 mm, whereas for females it was 21.63 ± 1.58 mm. The differences between these measurements were statistically significant with a p-value of less than 0.001 (**Table 1**).

The inner transverse diameter (TD) of the male cricoid was 15.66 ± 2.16 mm and 10.54 ± 0.47 mm for females. The outer TD for males measured 23.83 ± 1.87 mm, while that for females was 17.86 ± 1 mm. These differences were also statistically significant at $p < 0.001$ (**Table 1**).

3.2 Measurements of Lamina of Cricoid- The thickness (TK) of the lamina was significantly greater in males (5.32 ± 0.64 mm) compared to females (3.93 ± 0.49 mm). The height (HT) of the lamina was 24.10 ± 0.96 mm in males and 18.57 ± 0.84 mm in females. These differences were statistically significant at $p < 0.001$ (**Table 1**).

3.3 Measurements of Arch of Cricoid- The thickness (TK) of the male cricoid arch was 3.24 ± 0.57 mm, while that of the female was 2.60 ± 0.39 mm; this difference was statistically significant at $p < 0.01$ (**Table 1**).

The height (HT) of the arch was 7.07 ± 0.66 mm in males and 5.39 ± 0.65 mm in females. Differences in height were statistically significant at $p < 0.001$ (**Table 1**).

Figure 1: Cricoid Cartilage; AB- Anteroposterior diameter, DC- Transverse diameter

Figure 2: Cricoid Cartilage; EF: Height of Cricoid Arch

Figure 3: Cricoid Cartilage; GH- Height of Cricoid Lamina

Table 1: Measurements of Cricoid Cartilage (In mm)

Variables		Male (10)	Female (10)
		Mean±SD	Mean±SD
APD	Inner	19.85±1.61	14.84±1.54***
	Outer	28.99±1.45	21.63±1.58***
TD	Inner	15.66±2.16	10.54±0.47***
	Outer	23.83±1.87	17.86±1***
TK Lamina		5.32±0.64	3.93±0.49***
HT Lamina		24.10±0.96	18.57±0.84***
TK ARCH		3.24±0.57	2.60±0.39**
HT Arch		7.07±0.66	5.39±0.65***

(***p<0.001, **p<0.01)

APD- Antero-posterior diameter, TD- Transverse diameter, TK of Lamina- Thickness of Lamina, HT Lamina- Height of Lamina, TK Arch-Thickness of arch, HT Arch- Height of arch

Table 2: Comparison of Cricoid cartilage measurements (in mm) of the present study with those from other Indian Studies

Parameters		Present Study Karnataka		Anand V et al., Karnataka ¹¹		Rajan Kumar Singla et al., Punjab ⁵		Saveetha et al., Karnataka ⁹	
		Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female
APD	Outer	28.99±1.45	21.63±1.58			20.01±3.8	19.89±1.41	23.84±2.43	19.18±2.34
	Inner	19.85±1.61	14.84±1.54	14.11 ±2.55	12.71 ±0.45	13.69±3.10	13.63±2.90		
TD	Outer	23.83±1.87	17.86±1			24.77±3.43	21.94±0.52	25.53±2.23	19.29±2.52
	Inner	15.66±2.16	10.54±0.47	17.52±2.64	15.05±1.02	12.99±2.38	9.12±1.38		
Height	Arch	7.07±0.66	5.39±0.65	7.69±0.63	6.5±0.68	7.56±1.15	7.0±0.53	5.97±0.94	4.94±1
	Lamina	24.10±0.96	18.57±0.84	21.17 ±2.31	18.38 ±0.61	21.81±2.93	18.55±0.65	21.3±1.9	17.91±2.29
Thickness	Arch	3.24±0.57	2.60±0.39	2.55±0.14	2.08±0.16	3.31±0.83	2.91±0.31		
	Lamina	5.32±0.64	3.93±0.49	2.82 ±0.14	2.43 ±0.11	5.21±0.83	4.71±0.22		

APD- Antero-posterior diameter, TD- Transverse diameter

IV. DISCUSSION

The growing use of advanced, radiological, electrophysiological, and surgical techniques in diagnosing and treating laryngeal disorders necessitates a deep understanding of the size and proportions of the human larynx and its cartilaginous components [3, 7]. While there are limited reports on the measurements of the cricoid cartilage, significant variations have been noted among different regions of India. Table 2 compares the dimensions of cricoid cartilages across various Indian populations, revealing slight differences in their sizes. The present study was conducted in the North-western part of Karnataka (Belagavi). The findings demonstrated a significant difference between the dimensions of male and female cricoid cartilages (p < 0.001), with all measured dimensions being larger in males compared to females.

The current study demonstrated a significant difference between the AP diameter and TD (p<0.001). The average inner AP diameter was greater than the inner TD. Similarly, a study by Joshi et al., reported an AP diameter of 19.29 ± 2.47 mm and a TD of 18.33 ± 2.26 mm [8]. Furthermore, another study reported that the inner AP diameter greater than the inner TD (Table 2) [5]. In the present study, the outer AP diameter measured 28.99 ± 1.45 mm in males, while in females, it was 21.63 ± 1.58 mm. The outer TD was 23.83 ± 1.87 mm in males and 17.86 ± 1.00 mm in females. The mean value of the outer AP diameter in the present study was higher compared to reports from Singla et al., and Saveetha et al., where TD diameter was greater [5,9].

A study examining the cricoid cartilage in a Nigerian population reported an AP diameter of 28.82 ± 4.07 mm for males and 24.06 ± 2.53 mm for females. The TD was measured at 29.84 ± 6.10 mm in males and 25.84 ± 3.48 mm in females. This finding is in contrast to our study, where the TD was found to be lower [4]. Another study on German cricoid cartilage showed that the AP diameter in males was 30.90 ± 3.06 mm

and in females, it was 25.20 ± 2.33 mm [3]. When comparing diameters across different populations, both AP and TD diameters are smaller in the Indian population. In comparison with other Indian studies, our findings revealed that the TD and AP diameters were higher.

The mean height of the arch was found to be 7.07 ± 0.66 mm for males and 5.39 ± 0.65 mm for females. The mean height of the lamina was 24.10 ± 0.96 mm in males and 18.57 ± 0.84 mm in females. These results were consistent with the findings of Anand V et al., and Singla et al., [10, 5] although the height of the lamina in males was slightly higher in the present study.

Additionally, the mean heights of the lamina reported for Nigerians (male: 26.50 ± 6.30 , female: 24.50 ± 5.32 mm), Germans (male: 24.60 ± 1.84 mm, female: 21.30 ± 1.44 mm) and Europeans (male: 25.3 mm, female 20.7 mm) were greater than those observed in the present study [3, 4, 11].

The mean value of thickness of arch was 3.24 ± 0.57 mm for males and 2.60 ± 0.39 mm for females. The mean thickness of the lamina was 5.32 ± 0.64 mm in males and 3.93 ± 0.49 mm in females. These values were in alignment with the reports from Singla et al.,[5].

The morphometry of the cricoid cartilage showed variation among the Indian population (Table 2). In this study, the AP diameter and TD diameter were greater than those reported in other Indian studies, while the diameters were smaller in females compared to males. These differences might be attributed to variations in body shape and ethnicity. When compared to other races (Europeans and Nigerians), the dimensions of the Indian cricoid cartilage were smaller. This indicates that measurements can differ across various populations. Therefore, using the same type of endotracheal tubes for intubation across different populations, races, and sexes may risk damaging the laryngeal membrane. Hence, these measurements will aid in selecting appropriate endotracheal tubes.

V. CONCLUSION

The present study measured all the dimensions of the cricoid cartilage and found that the AP diameter was greater than the TD diameter, with both dimensions being slightly larger compared to other Indian populations. This morphometric data will be valuable in choosing the right endotracheal tubes for intubation and for surgical procedures involving the larynx.

CONFLICTS OF INTERESTS: None

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